

Science School Was Burned: A Case Study of Crisis Management in Thailand

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Abstract—This study analyzes the crisis management and image repair strategies during the crisis of Mahidol Wittayanusorn School (MWIT) library burning. The library of this school was burned by a 16-year-old-male student on June 6th, 2010. This student blamed the school that the lesson was difficult, and other students were selfish. Although no one was in the building during the fire, it had caused damage to the building, books and electronic supplies around 130 million bahts (4.4 million USD). This event aroused many discourses arguing about the education system and morality. The strategies which were used during crisis were denial, shift the blame, bolstering, minimization, and uncertainty reduction. The results of using these strategies appeared after the crisis. That was the numbers of new students, who registered for the examination to get into this school in the later years, have remained the same.

Keywords—School, crisis management, violence, image repair strategies, uncertainty, burn.

I. INTRODUCTION

A crisis for the educational system in Thailand was noted after a student burnt the library of Mahidol Wittayanusorn school (MWIT) [1]. Around 2:00 AM of June 6th, 2010, 10 fire engines tried to stop the fire at building No.2 of the school. After the fire, the 1st to 4th floors were totally damaged. This event was caused by a 16-year-old male student, who was studying in grade 11. He bought a lighter and a liter of benzene in front of the school, and he brought them into the 2nd floor of the library in building No.2. He hid there until the library closed at 9:00 PM of June 5th. After he burnt the library, he went to hide in a restroom at the food court. He tried to call the emergency number (191) many times, after he found that the fire expanded to other areas beyond his expectation. After this event, the school asked other students to leave the school for seven days, and they came back to begin the class again on June 14th, 2010.

II. MAHIDOL WITTAYANUSORN SCHOOL

Mahidol Wittayanusorn has been the best school in Thailand in the field of science, mathematics and computers [2]. This is because the high numbers of students who succeed to enter high-ranking universities and many awards the students earn from scholar competitions. After the 11th class year (2001), this school turned into a new system, which has been used until now. Every year, around 20,000 grade-9

students register for the school admission examination, and about 500 students will be selected to attend the second-round examination. These 500 students need to stay in the school about 3-4 days. During the short period of camping, they are asked to work on the scientific laboratory, taking the EQ and IQ examinations and taking the science and mathematics examinations with new and strange problems. Finally, 240 students will be selected. They are separated into 10 classes, 24 students per each. Two teachers are assigned to adviser each class [3].

As a 12th-class-year student in 2005, the researcher heard from the 10th-class-year students that the school had moved from Rai King temple (Wat Rai King). The old classrooms in the temple were made with wood and zinc roofing sheets. The classrooms were sometimes wet during the rainy season. A year after moving to the new place, the school director and the founder, Dr. Thongchai Chewprecha talked about establishing a big and modern library, and the new library was opened in the year the author finished the high school, Dr. Thongchai is a role model with a great willingness to help students and a commitment to Thai national identity, in particular, his concern is that Thailand needs more scientists and researchers to continue developing the country and create less dependency on foreign technology and knowledge. During 2002 to 2005, the researcher was in this school, we traveled to study at many research centers outside the school, we attended many seminar events spoken by professional scientists and related field. The school also provided us an evening study clinic, where the students could bring the questions to ask the teachers there. Sometimes, we made up classes at night or on Saturday, if the whole school missed the class.

We are not only proud of what have passed through; Dr. Thongchai also told that Princess Sirindhorn called this school, the school of Her grandfather or the father of our King. We are proud that we have a chance to call this school as our school. There is no doubt that many alumni and current students were very angry, when the library was burnt.

Although no one was dead, this event damaged the school's reputation. The public blamed school that they could not manage the relationship among knowledge, pleasure and value [4]. The public asked the same question as in Finland shooting, how this kind of act could ever happen in this context [5]. During the crisis, the researcher was an employee of a company, and some sarcastic words were told in the workplace about the researcher's background studying in MWIT.

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III. CRISIS MANAGEMENT

Ulmer, Sellnow & Seeger defined a crisis as the event that is unexpected, non-routine and the crisis may cause the changing in organization after the crisis [6], [7]. Coombs [8] classified crisis management into 3 categories to analyze the set of factors, which are pre-crisis, crisis and post crisis. During pre-crisis, crisis management seeks to prevent and prepare for the crisis. During crisis, stakeholders, property, public, financial resources and reputation assets need to be safe [9]. Timely response, good prior reputation, crisis management strategies and sufficient information will quickly help to bring the situation to a resolution [10].

If Mahidol Wittayanusorn (MWIT) library burning was classified in the type of crisis in situational crisis communication theory (SCCT), this event could be identified as malevolence, but it might not be in the victim cluster. No one was injured or dead, even though school could be considered as victim in this event. For this case alone, school required only very little attribution of crisis responsibility [11], but how the student blamed the school through the media, and how the school failed to prevent the crisis, led the school board and director to establish a strong attribution of crisis responsibility.

Fishman [12] argued there were two types of focusing event. Type one is normal or natural disaster, while type two could violate expectations. Type two is powerful, because it can influence public agenda [12], [13]. MWIT library burning is type two, and also an emergency event. The definition of emergency is a harmful effect of forces caused by humans or natural disasters. It is dangerous for life, health, property or environment [10]. After the fire occurred, MWIT needed to use image repair strategies and other related strategies to bring the situation back to normal and protect their reputation.

IV. METHODS

This research is an analysis of online text. The selected online news articles need to be in the official websites of actual newspapers printed in Thailand. Most websites of news reports are in a blog format, so the readers/subscribers can add their opinions in the part of comment. These online news articles are the main medium, that the readers use to receive the news, especially school alumni, who often study aboard. Newspapers are trusted among Thai people, since many Thai people in Facebook always share the news, photos and quotes from the actual newspaper. For regular online users, information in newspaper website is the most reliable source comparing with other websites, blogs and social networking posts.

After the online articles were selected, the interview contents and expert discussion in the articles was examined and arranged to fit into the strategies and theories. This study is interested in image repair strategies, crisis management, face threats, ethics and learning from crisis (discourse of renewal). These topics were used to describe the news articles along with the research objectives. The objectives of this

study are (1) to analyze the argument of the school members and the student who burnt the library through new media, (2) to identify their words along with image repair strategies, (3) to study their crisis management in pre-crisis, crisis and post crisis, and (4) to understand how these people used ethic during the crisis.

Note: *Since this study needed to call the student who burnt the school many times, so he would be called, "Sid" as his name used in this paper.*

Research Question:

- 1) What were MWIT's crisis management strategies in pre-crisis, crisis and post-crisis?
- 2) Which strategies or theories did MWIT and Sid use in these three phases?
- 3) What were the roles of media during crisis and post crisis?
- 4) How did the actors perform their ethic and moral during crisis?

V. FINDINGS

A. Image Attacks

The phase "face threats" is often used for an individual person, so for the organization, "image attacks" or "reputation attacks" will be more suitable words. Cornelissen's definition of "image" is the impression that outside stakeholders have for the organization [14]. A crisis can easily damage an image or reputation of the organization [15]. During crisis, MWIT's reputation was attacked from four sources, as following.

The first reputation attack was how Sid burnt and blamed the school. This case was slightly different from crisis type matrix [14]. Sid was a student, but he was not the employee of the school. Sid was still considered as inside stakeholder of the school. Regularly, terrorist refers to the attack of outsider, but for this case, Sid, the insider was the terrorist, who intended to harm the school's education system.

Second, media empowered Sid's statement. Power relations of media and outside sources regularly classify the media agenda into four types as 4-boxed-matrix model, low-or-high power of media and low-or-high power of sources [16]. Sid, a low power source, talked to media, which were high power sources, and then media published what he said. This situation was how Sid's statement had power over the school, and some audiences believed what he said. While media created more power for Sid, in the reality, comparing between power of Sid and the school, school had power over the future of the student.

The third attack was when the expert commented on the situation through the media. The expert was a researcher and lecturer outside MWIT, so media and public listened to him. This was similar to when Steve Jobs supported Foxconn by claiming that the suicide rate was still below the rate of the United States society. This support could cause dissatisfaction among Apple customers who concerned about Foxconn's suicide case [17]. The expert who commented about MWIT

was from Chulalongkorn University, which had a relationship with Chulalongkorn University Demonstration School and Triam Udom Suksa School. From the outsiders' point of views, both schools were considered as the competitors for MWIT, so MWIT stakeholders might not be happy. This might mean that the expert also tried to attack MWIT's image during the crisis, even if in fact, he tried to help.

Finally, some audiences of online news reports attacked the school image with their negative comments about the school. Klaver [18] stated that, a conative message intention has found to be positive for the trust level of followers. Online media deserve one step further than traditional newspaper that is their interaction with the audiences. Audiences could rely on the comments of other audiences, which sound reasonable, especially for the comments that contained the same views as them [19]. An interesting element in *Post Today* newspaper was that they selected the comment from their online news blog to print in their newspaper. They bring public agenda to be their media agenda. Unexpectedly, *Post Today* selected the negative comments about MWIT to show in their newspaper, which its targeted audiences were middle class people, who tended to be concerned about the crisis event and the future of the education in Thailand.

The agenda setting of these newspapers and their news blog created two different directions of spiral of silence, which are (1) people who believed that Sid was a bad student who has a mental disorder, and (2) people who believed that problem was at the education system of MWIT. For example, *Thaipost* [20] said, "Sid burnt the school, because he only needs to have a vacation" in its headline. This headline persuaded the audiences to blame Sid as a bad student. Yodpuang & Buachu [2] posted the statement of the Chulalongkorn University lecturer, saying that Sid was not wrong, but this should be a lesson for MWIT. This new blog would influence the audiences to be more concerned about the curriculum of the school.

The point was that how *Post Today* [21] put the negative comments of their online news blog on their actual newspaper caused a strong spiral of silence in a negative way for MWIT. Attribution theory also supports this type of spiral of silence that people would look for the reasons of the event, especially negative events [11], [22]. Since blogs are social media, and many of them are linked to social networking sites as Facebook, the audiences who read the negative comments from their fellows would trust that message, rather than the message sent by MWIT itself [18], [23]. These people kept saying the same things as they found in the media. Greenberg [24] stated a fact about risk communication, which is similar to crisis communication that the communication can fail only after a problem, has arisen and once public opinion has begun to take shape about what occurred and who is to blame. These were all reasons that MWIT needed to work harder in their crisis response.

Since media plays an active role during crisis [24], some newspapers were misled about the school, when they tried to say something bad on top of the bad news, and that was how

the school's image was more damaged. Komchadluek [3] posted that MWIT's failure was that only 20 percents of the students continued studying in Science, even the school received 100 million baht to produce more scientists. In fact, Dr. Thongchai allows the students to continue studying any field they like, but the requirement is that the students need to conduct research in their field to benefit the overall knowledge created in the country of Thailand.

Another misleading information in the news blog was when *OK Nation* [25] posted that Sid wore a yellow shirt while he burnt the school. After burning, Sid told *Matichon* newspaper that he mimicked adults' behavior. Regularly, people believe that the red shirt protesters in Thailand burned Central World shopping mall and other buildings. When *OK Nation* said, "yellow shirt" in the school burning news, audiences might translate that Sid mimicked the yellow shirt protesters who burned some building; even in fact, yellow shirt protesters did not burn any building. The "yellow shirt" which Sid wore is the school dormitory suit. All male students in MWIT wear yellow shirts, and all female students wear purple shirts. This political related news with the political-act imitation brought its audiences into the central route in elaboration likelihood model, which they really cared and considered much about the news. Since last five years, if the word, "crisis" was put in Google search box, the results had been mostly political.

B. Failure in Pre-Crisis State

There was no statement that MWIT really ignored the crisis warning sign or they did not. The news said that Sid tried to burn a couch and a column/pole two weeks before the crisis [25]. Yuvadee Nakapadungrat, MWIT school director also mentioned that Sid's parents told her to intentionally look after Sid at the beginning of the semester [26]. Both sources pointed out that MWIT could not prevent the crisis, although they knew the warning sign. This event was the most serious case that occurred in MWIT. Most of these students have never harmed anyone and anything in the school. The worst case which happened once before the crisis was only that a student broke the window and the door in the school. This means the event was not really one that could have been predicted, especially in the context in Thailand or MWIT. Although many school shootings occurred in other countries [27]-[31], a school burning should not occur in MWIT. MWIT is different from those schools, because most students have a high intention in studying, and they are considered as genius students. Sompong Jitradub, a Chulalongkorn University lecturer, suggested that MWIT should have advised Sid after he burnt a couch and a column, and if that had been done, it would be likely that, Sid would never try to burn the school again [1]. His suggestion was similar to crisis management plan that seeks preparation and prevention [32]. Prevention is to take an action onto the warning sign to reduce the possibility that risk becomes a crisis [33]. For the preparation, there was a doubt that Sid was the one who called the police to stop the fire. The question was why the security guard did not hear fire alarm.

School shooting was also an unexpected case in Scandinavian context, because of low rate of poverty [34], [5]. The library burning was a really unexpected case for MWIT, too. MWIT has a high quality of education. Every student was screened by IQ and EQ tests. They also pay allowance to their students every month. MWIT students receive both scholar and this allowance, which can be considered as "pre-giving" in compliance with gaining of strategy-choice model. Students should be happy with this pre-giving, and this pre-giving should be able to reduce their stresses.

C. Shift the Blame & Simple Denial

"Shift the blame" is one of image repair strategies in the category of denial. Once Sid found that he was wrong, he did not want to be blamed. Sid said to *Matichon* that, "I don't want to study here. Other students are selfish. The lesson is difficult. I can't follow the class. A lot of pressure is created by the teachers. That's why I consider mimicking what adults did [1]." How Sid claimed that other students were selfish, was similar to the case of school shooting in other country. The shooter was depicted as a victim of bullies in class and also in military [35]. Sid also used the strongest point of MWIT to create the weak point, when he said that the lesson was difficult. Before the crisis, most people believe that MWIT students are smart enough to understand this intensive lesson, but Sid attacked the school image by attacking this belief.

When the main media released negative information about the event, before the organization itself, this means MWIT could not act according to "stealing thunder," which is how the organization shapes the news before other sources try to damage its image [36]. After Sid shifted the blame to MWIT, it was MWIT's turn to shift the blame onto him. However, the school is an educational organization, so MWIT needed to make sure that their statements of blaming the student was true.

Normally, we understand the laws, that if one had a mental disorder, he would not be wrong. Sid's father interview content was posted in *Thaipost* [20], that Sid went back home only once a year in summer vacation; Sid complain that he was stressed from the class, and he did not want to go back to MWIT again. That was the pre-crisis period. Sid's father told the media that Sid might have a mental disorder, because many people in the same family also had mental disorder. Sid's father did not tell anyone before about Sid's mental disorder, because he was afraid that Sid would not have a chance to continue studying [1]. What Sid's father said was proved by Sid's friends. They told *Thaipost* [20], that Sid was always alone. Sid's GPA before getting into MWIT was 4.00, but after he moved here, his GPA was 3.10. Sid was serious about the problem, but when he asked other friends about his homework or the lesson, no one helped him. How Foxconn responded to the crisis, they blamed on the workers, because to blame them was easier than to change the system [37]. Similarly, Narissara Chawaltanpitak, deputy minister of education, confirmed that everyone had analyzed the event,

and found that Sid had an individual problem, which should not be related to the school [1]. Dr. Thongchai also supported that he did not believe that Sid's motivation was all about the school, but it should be affected from something else [2]. This is how the school did not really need any change after the crisis.

While Sid blamed MWIT and MWIT provided the information that it was not wrong at them, those who might be wrong could be the students themselves. All MWIT students lived in dormitories, so they would see their friends read the books, did the assignment or went to an evening studying clinic to discuss with the teacher. The students would compare their effort to the others, which led to a competition. A serious competition which was indicated by GPA could cause a lot of stress on the students. Prayudh Payutto [38] wrote in his book that nowadays, students understand that grade was more important than what they learned. He recommended that people would learn best, when they believed that the lesson was important to their future. This suggestion is similar to uncertainty reduction theory, which the people would try hard to learn and gather the information to reduce their uncertainty, when they are in a new situation [16].

Another statement which can be considered as "shift the blame" was when an MWIT alumnus blamed Sid's parents. Ayasit said that the event was not caused by the school's system, but it was about the parents, who used their child as a tool to win the social judgment, and created much stress on their child, so the parents should try to understand their child better than before [2].

D. Defeasibility

Defeasibility was an image repair strategy in the category of evading responsibility. Defeasibility means that the organization lacks information to control the crisis, or to prevent the crisis [11]. Yuvadee Nakapadungrat, the school director, said to *Bangkok Business News* [26], that Sid was normally a polite student who had a good attention in the class, and she had never found any abnormal appearance on Sid, so she did not really understand why Sid needed to burn the library. Narissara Chawaltanpitak, deputy minister of education, also confirmed that MWIT took care their students really nice, every student also helped each other and MWIT had never had any student with an unusual behavior [39].

Since every new student needed to pass a psychological test before get into the school [1], Dr. Thongchai said in *Komchadluek* newspaper, that this was a tiny leaking point, which was hard to be expected. The way to fix it was that teachers and older students must help to look after younger students.

E. Accidental

Accidental was another image repair strategy in the category of evading responsibility. Accidental means that the crisis can happen sometimes, and no one intends to make it happen [11]. Accidental strategy was used in the study of Zhang & Benoit [40], which explained how Chinese

government responded to SARS disease in China. For this case, Sid excused that he did not want to burn the whole library, but he only needed to burn a small part of it, so he could have a chance to have some vacation. He claimed that he could not really control the fire by himself, and that was why he called the police many times.

F. Good Intentions

Sid told the media that he had asked his friends, if they wanted to have a vacation during the semester. They told him that they also wanted it. At that moment, Sid thought that he intended to do a good thing, when he burned the library.

G. Bolstering

Bolstering is similar to "calling in debt" in compliance gaining of strategy-choice model [16], which is how the organization reminded the stakeholder or the public about good things they had done before the crisis. Not only image repair strategies that include bolstering in it, crisis response strategies also contain a bolstering posture. Pampers had used bolstering to remind their customers that they had worked hard to improve their products around 50 years [11], [41]. Taiwanese news reports also reminded the fans of Wang, a basketball player, about his past good work before the time that he lost the game [42]. The same in US government who mentioned how strict the process of American beef quality control during Mad Cow disease crisis [43].

Since school's board said good things about MWIT as shown in the D. part, "Defeasibility," MWIT alumni also talked about good past through newspaper's blogs. Ayasit and Ekkapong, alumni, confirmed that each student needed to perform the work for the society or engage in CSR activities about 40 hours per semester. They needed to go to camp to teach the younger students and to learn more about Buddhist truth [2], [26].

H. Differentiation

Differentiation is a part of diminishment posture of crisis response strategies and the strategy to reduce offensiveness in image repair strategies. Taiwanese news reported that even their sportsman hero, Wang, lost the game; he still performed better than other Asian players [42]. This was how his fans did not feel much upset from the news. Another study of the same researchers pointed how US government failed to repair their image in Mad Cow disease crisis, by saying that riding scooters in Taiwan was much dangerous than eating US beef product [43].

As in a previous discussion, Sid made differentiation by saying that he imitated the burning behavior of other adults, which was related to political crisis in Thailand. Sid tried to minimize his fault by comparing with a worse case. While Sid tried to minimize his fault, he also brought this news to be in the discussion of those who were engaged with political news.

Since the financial crisis spread around the world, because of the bankrupt of Lehman Brothers in 2008 [44], school crisis could also spread by imitation of bad behaviors. Post-Columbine shooters might mimic the acts of those Columbine

shooters [45], [46]. For MWIT, *OK Nation* [25] wrote that MWIT was not the first case of school burning, but it was a very important case for Thai people to concern about education, because MWIT have been a famous school. Burning behaviors were widely found in the north-east of Thailand, and it might be the imitation between the students, or it could be the imitation that the students imitated the protesters' action.

The copy-cat crime was found in the underground (subway) of London, which the bombers attempted to make a suicide bomb attack after the first bomb around two weeks [14]. Tawatchai Thaikyo, the director of child protection unit, cited a psychological finding that all criminal acts were founded by some inspiration, and the case of MWIT, the inspiration was the political related action, when the protesters burned down Central World shopping mall. Raittila, Koljonen & Välvirronen [35] referred to news that although police found the tapes recorded the criminal related action of the school shooters, they did not show it to the media, because of the fear that other students might inspire a copy-cat behavior.

Most research observations in the area of media violence are the relationship between media usage and aggressiveness, and many of them are the negative outcome of multitasking in class [47]. The research about school shooting also analyzed the musical taste of the shooters [46]. The research about political-related-action imitation in teenagers is still hard to find. This study suggests this variables need to be explored, and it would benefit the way to report political news. In Thai context, almost all songs, videos and movies are seriously filtered from the government. The lyrics of rock band in Thailand are not harmful as in the western countries. Many Thai famous artists also received awards from government organizations if they devoted themselves for the society or for their parents. If a Thai student had his aggressiveness because of the music, the music they listened to should be some western black metal band, not Thai band.

I. Mortification and Ethics Performance

Chokesikarin [48] found that one of the most important influences that customers chose hostels in Thailand was the image of the hostels. She performed the ethic by driving to the customers who lost their way in Bangkok. Ethic can be put in the category of mortification in image repair strategies, because the crisis actor shows how he concerns about the situation. This act will lead the stakeholders to forgive him.

Firstly, the communicator needs to understand what the audience concerns and believe about the crisis [49]. While Sid blamed the school that other students were selfish and a lot of pressure was created by the teachers, Dr. Thongchai and Yuvadee, the school director responded to this image attack very nicely. They allowed Sid to come back to study in MWIT and added that the student needed to make a decision by himself, because other friends might blame him for his past acts [39]. Dr. Thongchai and Yuvadee did not bring this event into the court, but they let the police to do what the laws ask to do [50].

MWIT did not only show the contrast between who they really were and what Sid blamed, they showed how they treated a student as an important stakeholder, too. They understood that it would be hard for Sid to get into other schools with this bad reputation. How MWIT responded to the crisis was very different from Foxconn, who failed to recognize their workers as important stakeholders [17].

Foxconn did not care enough on their employees, because during that period, many people looked for a job [37]. In fact, around 20,000 students always come to take the competition entrance exam to get into MWIT [51]. While MWIT was one of the most wanted places for high school students, they never forgot that Sid was their student, who they needed to look after. Since that, Dr. Thongchai and Yuvadee were considered as the leaders who have values of ethical leadership [52].

Moreover, Dr. Thongchai showed his sincerity by crying during the interview. Similarly, Mayor Giuliani were angry during the interview about 9/11 attack. He went to several funerals. He talked about the recovery. The values of his communication could work really well in crisis response [6]. This is similar to an argument Coombs and Holladay [53] made, that apology and sympathy are more successful strategy comparing with the information. Dr. Thongchai's responses were similar. He was an ethical leader and he was sincere, so his response could be successful, too.

With Buddhist background of almost all Thai people, we believe that to give things to a nice man is better than give things to a poor man; to give things to an enlightened person or Buddha is better than to give things to a nice man; and to give things for public is better that to give things to an enlightened person. In the other word, Buddhists' belief is about I-Though relationship, which is the way to act and look, how the group or whole society is more important than oneself [16].

Library is a public place. To burn a library, Sid would receive a heavy sin. Buddhists would blame on Sid rather than to blame on school. Another type of giving in Buddhist belief is to give others the knowledge. This merit would cause the giver to be an intelligent person or guru in the future. Library is also a place that carries a large amount of knowledge [25]. This was another reason that Sid was to blame in Buddhist society. Because of these believes, MWIT did not take a long time to turn the crisis back to normal.

How Buddhists concern about public, agreed with Coombs [11], that public safety should be the first priority in the crisis. After MWIT library was burned, MWIT announced that everyone needed to leave the school and dormitory for a week. The engineers needed to make sure that the building would not fall down, since 1st to 4th floors were burned.

If Sid and those school shooters were compared, Sid was more ethical than them. Most school shooters killed other people and then killed themselves [54]-[57]. Sid did not kill anybody, because he burnt the library at night. Moreover, he called the police after he found that fire expanded to many areas of the building. After the crisis, Sid was checked if he had mental disorder, and he said that if he could move back to

the time before the crisis, he would not do it. Although Sid was blamed from public, he still respected other human-beings.

The previous discussions present all image repair strategies used by both MWIT and Sid. In this section, the discussion and suggestion will be about post-crisis stage.

J. Uncertainty Reduction

Normally, the lack of information leads to uncertainty [16]. After crisis, all the students and their parents would fall into the feeling of uncertainty. Although the crisis was not too complex for them to understand, they could not be sure to come back to school again. A similar question was asked after Columbine school shooting, that when the students would be able to return to the school [58]. MWIT students might feel frightened, anxious and depressed [5]. Stoklasa, Starzyczna & Sykorova [59] found that their participants' purchasing behaviors were changed during the crisis. The learning outcome and emotion of MWIT students might be affected by the crisis, too. Princess Sirindhorn worried about these effects, so she suggested that school needed to have some activities to reduce uncertainty and create more trust [26]. In June, 14th 2010, all students came back to the school [50], [26]. Many alumni went to school to run the activities for the current students. The activities created an intimacy, which negatively correlated with the level of uncertainty [16]. While many students and their parents might feel that it was not safe to come to the school, the trust which was created in the activity could decrease the level of estimate of risk [60].

K. Discourse of Renewal

Discourse of renewal looks at the future rather than the crisis itself. The organization can rebuild the company, learn from crisis, and improve organization's system [6]. Buddhist teaching is similar to discourse of renewal. Buddhadasa Bhikkhu [61], an influential-ascetic-Buddhist philosopher, said that those who were smart could find the happiness, while they were suffering. Kris Nimmalo [62] extended this quote that most people wanted to turn the crisis to the place before the crisis happened, but Buddha taught that we needed to accept the current situation, and looked for a good thing and a new opportunity.

Not so long after the crisis event, MWIT announced that they would rebuild the library. The estimate damaged property was around 130 million baht (4.4 million USD), and MWIT needed 100 million baht (3.4 million USD) to rebuild the library and the 3rd and 4th floors, which were classrooms [26]. During the rebuilding process, MWIT built 15 temporary classrooms, and transform the old library at the 4th floor of building No.1 to be a temporary library [50]. The original number of books in the burnt library was around 70,000 books, and only one week after the event, people donated around 15,000 books to the school. MWIT still needed more books, especially science textbooks in English language [50].

For the case of fire at Cole Hardwood and at Malden Mill, the entrepreneur spent too much money to pay their

employees and to rebuild [6]. Although MWIT needed to spend a large amount of money, the government organization supported them. Moreover, Princess Sirindhorn would help, if only the school asked for Her help [39], [26].

According to the Section A, *Post Today* newspapers printed negative comments about MWIT on their newspaper during crisis. Schultz, Utz & Göritz [7] found that Twitter users were more probable to share the newspaper articles than blog posts and tweets of other users. *Post Today* online blog is newspaper article in a blog format, which is more reliable than an anonymous blog post. Downs [63] drew an issue-attention cycle graph, of which the highest point of this graph is, "briefly dominate attention," when people talked and were concerned much in crisis [58].

MWIT needed to rebuild library, classrooms and their reputation. They learned a similar thing as the case of Domino's pizza. Since the crisis of Domino's Pizza was created in Youtube, the way to solve the problem was to response the crisis in Youtube to reach the relevant audiences [6]. MWIT chose to paste the school advertising on the cover page of *Post Today* newspaper. This advertising contained the pictures of the student playing rock concert and enjoying the school activities. Dr. Thongchai said that the school had many places for students to relax, including music instrument rooms, cinema auditorium, karaoke room, sport center and many activity clubs. In the past, Dr. Thongchai did not like rock music, and he complained that some students played music too loud. In the advertising in *Post Today* newspaper was different. MWIT showed that they have learned from crisis.

L. Unuseful Suggestion for the Case

Wachira Pengchan, Deputy Director General of the Mental Health Department, suggested to the students that whenever they found they got some problems, they needed to tell their parents, their teachers and their friends. This is because these people loved them and were nice to them [64]. Tawatchai Thaikyo, director of child protection unit, commented that nowadays the school was too intensive on the lesson, and the students had lack of EQ; this was like two sides of a coin, of which another side might have a problem and no one saw it; the suggestion was that every school needed to have psychologists to advice the students [64].

These suggestions of important people in Thailand were made in the interviews according to MWIT library burning crisis. Although these suggestions might help other schools, but they did not really help MWIT in its future. Sid had already told his parents about the problem, and his parents had already told the teachers to look after Sid. MWIT had already had EQ screening examination, and had four psychologists to advice the students.

Muschert [58] described how the school needed prevention strategies, because of school shooting. However, Borum, Cornell, Modzeleski & Jimerson [65] argued that zero tolerance did little security in learning environment, school should screen the students, provide psychological first aid,

and also provided students the opportunities to express their feelings after crisis [32], [66]. These scholar suggestions did not help much in MWIT crisis. The suggestion is that the school should find the way to reduce competition between the students.

M.No Need to Change

Yuvadee confirmed that the school had already had a good system to look after all students. Every class had two advisers, and there were only 24 students in each class, and teachers did not force students [26]. As section C. Shift the Blame & Simple Denial mentioned about the statement of Narissara Chawaltanpitak, deputy minister of education, everyone concluded that the crisis was created from the individual problem, which was not related to the school's educational system [1]. Although ML. Panadda Dissakul, the Governor of Nakhon Pathom, suggested that the school should add more activities to fill more EQ into the students, Kritsanapong Keeratikor, an advisor of Mahidol Wittayanusorn school informed that the school had already had a good system to manage students' emotional maturity and already had the activities to empower the students to be nice people [1]. For example, school did a lot of CRS activities, such as students went to clean the temples, and the student traveled to nurseries of orphans.

Section G. Bolstering mentioned that two alumni supported the school that school had already had CSR activities, which the student would go outside and make things better for the society. Ekkapong believed that these were the way to reduce stress for every student [26]. These CSR activities before the crisis helped MWIT to rebuild their image after crisis. An interesting view is that the organization may forget to look how the employees think about CRS activities, such they may not like it although the outsiders like it [67]. As an alumnus, who might have a different point of views, CSR activities and sport activities of MWIT might be too hard. That moment, every student had to record their activities in a book, and the school would count the hours of working in the activities from that book. In each semester, each student had to work in CRS activities outside the school for 40 hours, worked in CRS-like activities inside the school for 40 hours, and played sports for 40 hours. During three years period of grade 10 to 12, we also needed to read 50 books from the list that school gave to us, which were not about the class.

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Sompong Jitradub, a lecturer of Chulalongkorn University said that teachers should not blame that Sid had a mental disorder, because the crisis reflected the lesson for the teachers. Sid dared to say the truth, but the school members felt painful and did not want to listen to him. While many students received awards from scholar competition, the school did not think about those students who could not follow the class. The students who were the losers of this competition reflected the dead period of education that the losers had to leave the game [2]. Sid did not have a mental disorder when he burnt the school. This was a crisis of the education, which the school need to reform the curriculum,

- Communication Theory (SCCT) and stealing thunder". *23rd EMAC Doctoral Colloquium. Copenhagen, Denmark: Copenhagen Business School*. 2010.
- [37] J. Chan, "A Suicide Survivor: The Life of Chinese Worker", *New Technology, Work and Employment*, vol. 28(2), 2013, p. 84-99
- [38] Prayudh Payutto. Dawn of Education (4th Edition). *Chiangrai: Saha Thammic*, 1990.
- [39] Banmuang Newspapers. "Princess Sirindhorn worried about Mahidol Wittayanusorn", June 8th, 2010, Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from <http://www.ryt9.com/s/bmnd/915793>
- [40] E. Zhang and W. L. Benoit, "Former Minister Zhang's Discourse on SARS: Government's Image Restoration or Destruction?", *Public Relations Review*, vol. 35, 2009, p. 240-246.
- [41] C. Burmann, T. Halaszovich, and F. Hemmann, "Identitätsbasierte Markenführung", *Springer Gabler*, 2012.
- [42] W. Wen, T. Yu and W. L. Benoit, "Our Hero Wang Can't be Wrong! A Case Study of Collectivistic Image Repair in Taiwan", *Chinese Journal of Communication*, vol. 2(2), 2009, p. 174-192.
- [43] W. Wen, T. Yu and W. L. Benoit, "The Failure of 'Scientific' Evidence in Taiwan: A Case Study of International Image Repair for American Beef", *Asian Journal of Communication*, vol. 22(2). 2012, p. 121-139.
- [44] B. Şakar, "International Financial Crises and the Political Economy of Financial Reforms in Turkey: 1994-2009", *International Journal of Social, Human Science and Engineering*, vol. 3(12), 2009, p. 1-7.
- [45] R.W. Larkin, "The Columbine Legacy: Rampage Shootings as Political Acts", *American Behavioral Scientist*, vol. 52(9), 2009, p. 1309-1326.
- [46] T. Kiilakoshi and A. Oksanen, "Soundtrack of the School Shootings: Cultural Script, Music and Male Rage", *Young*, vol. 19(3), 2011, p. 247-269.
- [47] P.Arunrangsiwed, R. Komonsevin, S. Kongtieng, O. Pasvekin and U. Pasvekin, "Never Text in Class: A Meta-Regression Analysis of The Relationship between Social Networking Sites Use and Academic Performances", *International Conference on Interdisciplinary Social Sciences. Vancouver: Common Ground*. 2014.
- [48] V. Chokesikarin, "Entrepreneurial Orientation and Customers Satisfaction: Evidences nearby Khao San Road", *International Journal of Social, Human Science and Engineering*, vol. 8(1), 2014, p. 71-76.
- [49] R. E. Lundgren and A. H. McMakin, *Risk Communication: A Handbook for Communicating Environment, Safety, and Health Risks (5th Edition)*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. 2013.
- [50] ASTV Manager Online (a). (2010, 14 June). MWIT Reopen: Announce, need more English Textbook. Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from <http://www.manager.co.th/QOL/ViewNews.aspx?NewsID=9530000081785>
- [51] Mahidol Wittayanudorn School. "Admission Examination 2012 Memorandum". 2012, Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from <https://www.mwit.ac.th/~academic/enlist/admission-2555.pdf>
- [52] D. R. G. Padgett, S. S. Cheng and V. Parek, "The Quest for Transparency and Accountability: Communicating Responsibly to Stakeholders in Crises", *Asian Social Science*, vol. 9(9), 2013.
- [53] W. T.Coombs, and S. J. Holladay, "Further explorations of post-crisis communication: Effects of media and response strategies on perceptions and intentions". *Public Relations Review*, vol. 35(1), 2009, p. 1-6.
- [54] P. Langman, "To Kill and To Die: Suicide and School Shooters", August 4th, 2009, Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from <http://www.psychologytoday.com/blog/keeping-kids-safe/200908/kill-and-die-suicide-and-school-shooters>
- [55] A. Rogers, "Why Do Gunmen Kill Themselves After Committing Mass Shootings?". December 28th, 2012, Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from www.businessinsider.com/suicide-and-mass-shootings-2012-12
- [56] The Associated Press. "12-year-old Nevada middle school shooter was bullied, left two suicide notes: police", May 14th, 2014, Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from <http://www.nydailynews.com/news/national/nevada-middle-school-shooter-left-2-suicide-notes-cops-article-1.1791820>
- [57] K. H. Kowalski, "2 Injured In Colorado High School Shooting, Gunman Committed Suicide". December 13th, 2013, Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from <http://hollywoodlife.com/2013/12/13/centennial-colorado-school-shooting-arapahoe-high-school/>
- [58] G. W. Muschert, Frame-changing in the media coverage of a school shooting: The rise of Columbine as a national concern, vol. 46, 2009, p. 164-170.
- [59] M. Stoklasa, H. Starzyczna and P. Sykorova, "Behavior of Czech Consumers during Crisis", *International Journal of Social, Human Science and Engineering*, vol. 8(3), 2014, p. 134-137.
- [60] G. Cvetkovich and P. L. Winter, "Social Trust and the Management of Risks to Threatened and Endangered Species", *Annual Meeting of the Society for Risk Analysis. Seattle, Washington*, 2001.
- [61] Buddhadasa Bhikkhu. "Gain Happiness from Sadness". September, 2007, Retrived 11th May, 2014, from <http://www.oknation.net/blog/print.php?id=122553>
- [62] Kris Nimmalo, "Dhamma Video", 2013, Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from <http://www.nimmalo.com/new/index.php/video>
- [63] A. Downs, "Up and Down With Ecology: The 'Issue-Attention Cycle'", *The Public Interest*, vol. 28(Summer), 1972, p. 38-50.
- [64] ASTV Manager Online (b) "Sent Burner- Suggest Genius School Needs Psychologists". June 7th, 2010, Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from <http://www.manager.co.th/QOL/ViewNews.aspx?NewsID=9530000078325>
- [65] R. Borum, D. Cornell, W. Modzeleski and S. Jimerson, "What Can Be Done About School Shootings?: A Review of the Evidence", *Educational Researcher*, vol. 39(1), 2010, p. 27-37.
- [66] S. E. Brock and S. R. Jimerson, "School crisis interventions: Strategies for addressing the consequences of crisis events". *Sacramento, CA: California Association of School Psychologists*, 2002.
- [67] S. May, O. Ihlen and J. L. Bartlett, *The Handbook of Communication and Corporate Social Responsibility (5th Edition)*. John Wiley & Sons. 2014.
- [68] ASTV Manager Online. "Intensive Examination Grade 10 Mahidol Wittayanusorn-Chulaporn Second Round needs GPA 3.00", July 16th, 2009, Retrived May 11th, 2014, from <http://www.manager.co.th/QOL/ViewNews.aspx?NewsID=9520000080361>
- [69] Wikipedia, "โรงเรียนที่ลดวิชาอนุสรณ์", May 5th, 2014, Retrieved 11th May, 2014, from <http://th.wikipedia.org/wiki/โรงเรียนที่ลดวิชาอนุสรณ์>
- [70] Mahidol Wittayanusorn School, "Mahidol Wittayanusorn School (Public Organization)", 2014, Retrieved May 11th, 2014, from <https://www.mwit.ac.th/>
- [71] B. Steyn, "Model for Developing Corporate Communication Strategy", *Communicare*, vol. 19(2), 2000, p. 1-33.

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